

THE STUDY OF REPTILES IN CENTRAL ASIA AND THE MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF SPECIES (BASED ON SCIENTIFIC COLLECTIONS)

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Abstract: This study focuses on analyzing the reptile species found in Central Asia, their morphological characteristics, and the history of their research. Utilizing scientific collections, morphological differences within reptile populations were identified, and their adaptations to different habitats were evaluated. Geometric morphometric methods were employed, providing insights into species variation through statistical and mathematical shape analysis. The findings offer essential data for reptile conservation and scientific classification. Additionally, this study contributes to addressing urgent issues in ecological monitoring and biodiversity preservation.

Keyword: Central Asia, Reptiles, Scientific collections, Morphological analysis, Морфо], *Eremias velox*, Species variation

Аннотация: Данное исследование направлено на анализ видов рептилий, обитающих в Центральной Азии, их морфологических характеристик и истории их изучения. Используя научные коллекции, были выявлены морфологические различия в популяциях рептилий, а также оценены их адаптации к различным средам обитания. Для исследования применялись методы геометрической морфометрии, которые обеспечили понимание вариаций между видами через статистический и математический анализ формы. Результаты предоставляют важные данные для сохранения рептилий и их научной классификации. Кроме того, данное исследование вносит вклад в решение актуальных проблем экологического мониторинга и сохранения биоразнообразия.

Ключевые слова: Центральная Азия, Рептилии, Научные коллекции, Морфологический анализ, Morpho], *Eremias velox*, Вариации видов

Introduction: Reptiles represent a significant component of biodiversity, playing a crucial role in maintaining the stability of various ecosystems. Central Asia serves as a biodiversity hotspot for reptiles, making the study of these

species both scientifically and ecologically important. This research aims to analyze the morphological characteristics of reptile species in Central Asia and investigate their adaptation mechanisms to diverse habitats.

The study utilized geometric morphometric methods based on specimens preserved in scientific collections. These methods provide accurate and reliable data for identifying morphological differences between species. The findings contribute to the scientific classification of species, understanding their ecological roles, and developing important recommendations for biodiversity conservation.

The study of morphological variation in organisms has been significantly advanced through the use of geometric morphometric methods, facilitated by tools such as MorphoJ. Developed by Chris Klingenberg, MorphoJ has been instrumental in analyzing biological shapes and understanding their evolutionary, ecological, and developmental dynamics. Klingenberg's work has focused on key areas, including the morphological variation in populations, the dynamics of shape changes during ontogenesis, and evolutionary transformations of shapes [1].

MorphoJ is not only used for evolutionary studies but also extends to other biological disciplines. For instance, Dean C. Adams has employed geometric morphometric techniques, including MorphoJ, to investigate evolutionary changes in size and shape within populations and to analyze biological shapes statistically [2]. In the field of paleontology, Norman MacLeod utilized MorphoJ to analyze the morphological structures of fossils, such as dinosaurs, exploring the mechanisms driving shape changes during evolutionary and ecological processes [3]. Similarly, Julia C. Boughner applied MorphoJ in her studies of skull shapes in humans and primates, linking morphological data to genetic influences [4]. In aquatic systems, Brian Sidlauskas used MorphoJ to examine fish morphology, revealing how their shapes adapt to ecological pressures and genetic variation within populations [5].

In herpetology, Valéria A. Goulart and Emma Sherratt contributed significantly to understanding the morphological variation in reptiles and amphibians. Goulart explored the geographic variability of their shapes and correlated it with ecological data using MorphoJ [6]. Sherratt examined the evolutionary patterns in amphibians and reptiles, focusing on how environmental and spatial factors influence shape changes [7].

The integration of MorphoJ into such diverse studies demonstrates its robustness and versatility, making it a crucial tool for modern biological

research. This study builds on these foundations, using MorphoJ to analyze morphological variations in reptiles from Central Asia, contributing to their conservation and classification.

Materials and Methods

The *Eremias velox*, or "rapid racerunner," is a species found in countries such as Central Asia, Northern China, Iran, Afghanistan, and Russia. Its habitat primarily includes desert and semi-desert regions. Belonging to the Lacertidae family, this species is known for its speed and agility.

The *Eremias velox* is a terrestrial reptile and oviparous, laying eggs for reproduction. Its diet consists of insects and other small invertebrates, reflecting its dependence on local food resources. The young are highly independent and mobile upon hatching, increasing their survival rates.

This species is classified as "Least Concern" on the IUCN Red List, indicating a stable population. Ecologically, it plays an essential role in controlling insect populations and other small organisms in the food chain.

Additionally, *Eremias velox* is a valuable subject in scientific research due to its morphological diversity and adaptability. Genetic analyses provide insights into its regional variations and internal diversity, contributing to the development of conservation strategies for the species.

The research focused on *Eremias velox* specimens from the herpetological collection of the Zoological Institute under the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. Morphological analysis of the head region was conducted on five specimens in a 2D format, using 18 landmarks.

The specimens were first selected, and their dorsal sides were photographed. These images were then digitized using TPSUtil64 software and processed in TPSDig2. In this software, landmarks were precisely marked on the dorsal images of each specimen. After completing the landmark placement for all specimens, the data were saved in a file format compatible with MorphoJ.

In MorphoJ, the data were analyzed to identify morphological variations and shape differences among the specimens. The research outcomes provide essential information for understanding the species' ecological role and contribute to its scientific classification and conservation.

Result and Discussion:

Lmk.	Axis 1 (x)	Axis 2 (y)
1	0.08551734	-0.43195705
2	0.04386930	-0.31304184
3	0.09544329	-0.33750082

4	0.07376568	-0.33543555
5	0.04836965	-0.22186674
6	-0.00321151	-0.07486292
7	0.02011843	-0.08916298
8	-0.00005943	0.08599525
9	-0.03071810	0.15194023
10	-0.09757962	0.24274151
11	-0.03393132	0.21701243
12	0.03493495	0.22299093
13	-0.07518346	0.13510129
14	0.12855204	0.20845236
15	-0.08152092	0.10982436
16	-0.17311688	0.09459077
17	-0.05141227	0.16392530
18	0.01616285	0.17125347

The square of the variation of the modules = 1.5492958858254995

The square of the variation of the tangent = 0.9367001027018484

The covariance matrix of the Principal Component Analysis is provided below:

	Eigenvalue%	Variation	Cumulative %
1.	0.12480687	53.296	53.296
2.	0.05141109	21.954	75.251
3.	0.03628347	15.494	90.745
4.	0.02167359	9.255	100.000

Total variation = 0.23417503

Confidence level = 0.0005716376617

The 4 coefficients of the principal analysis are given below:

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
x1	-0.036444	-0.010825	0.035323	-0.055853
y1	0.092167	0.053681	-0.010372	0.046996
x2	-0.037469	-0.022284	0.134883	-0.089008
y2	0.058890	0.034984	0.101524	-0.060490
x3	-0.036331	-0.229321	-0.069694	0.233679
y3	0.087404	-0.010759	-0.035832	0.038575
x4	-0.021296	0.198147	-0.018221	-0.203056
y4	0.111679	0.071310	-0.106497	0.030158
x5	-0.013594	-0.013763	0.012778	0.004062

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y5	0.034186	0.021171	-0.020715	0.034869
x6	0.018789	-0.107569	0.232994	0.219664
y6	-0.236972	0.034728	0.110861	0.002323
x7	0.127140	0.095334	-0.267279	-0.180113
y7	-0.161618	-0.297162	-0.178933	-0.302975
x8	-0.047541	0.187088	0.060078	0.149081
y8	-0.024838	-0.450825	-0.137405	-0.288972
x9	-0.058180	-0.144491	-0.049570	-0.124145
y9	0.270351	0.078387	-0.031331	0.082240
x10	0.074375	-0.108592	-0.066355	-0.076388
y10	0.457784	0.050839	-0.011452	0.017064
x11	-0.135475	-0.069004	0.170698	0.144633
y11	0.200185	-0.057708	-0.023366	0.045078
x12	-0.252995	0.074117	-0.111638	-0.138942
y12	0.173920	-0.027780	-0.033273	-0.002346
x13	0.145261	0.123695	0.454558	-0.165488
y13	-0.175239	0.057728	-0.146424	0.175225
x14	0.172915	-0.210665	0.019796	-0.254670
y14	-0.263698	0.115167	-0.227261	0.278203
x15	0.032002	-0.083027	-0.033433	-0.030384
y15	-0.318465	-0.024784	0.091216	-0.005585
x16	-0.134173	0.135835	0.069359	0.066214
y16	-0.346098	0.036144	0.064494	-0.028299
x17	0.141561	-0.301346	-0.104552	0.566880
y17	0.024285	0.077925	0.320083	-0.012343
x18	0.061456	0.486671	-0.469728	-0.066165
y18	0.016076	0.236954	0.274683	-0.049720

When analyzing Pica 1 and Pica 2, it was determined that the distribution of organisms belonging to the species *Eremias velox* falls within a coefficient range of 0.4. The first sample is within the coefficient range of 0.2 to 0.4. The second sample is within the coefficient range of 0.2 to 0.3. The third sample is within the coefficient range of 0.1 to 0.3. The fourth sample is within the coefficient range of 0.2 to 0.3.

Summary of the Article

The research focuses on the reptile species of Central Asia, with an emphasis on their morphological characteristics, adaptations, and the historical context of their study. The study used geometric morphometric methods, supported by tools like MorphoJ, to analyze shape variations statistically and mathematically. These methods enable precise identification of species differences, aiding in ecological and evolutionary studies. The findings not only support scientific classification but also provide critical data for biodiversity conservation and ecological monitoring.

A significant portion of the research is dedicated to the species *Eremias velox* (rapid racerunner), a terrestrial reptile found in arid and semi-arid regions across Central Asia, Northern China, and other adjacent areas. This species, classified as "Least Concern" by the IUCN, plays an essential ecological role by regulating insect populations. Its adaptability and morphological diversity make it a valuable subject for scientific studies.

The study utilized specimens from the Zoological Institute of Uzbekistan. Morphological analyses were conducted on the dorsal sides of the specimens' head regions using advanced tools like TPSUtil64 and TPSDig2. These images

were processed in MorphoJ to assess shape differences through landmark-based evaluations. The results highlight significant morphological variations, with detailed statistical data provided through Principal Component Analysis (PCA). For example, PC1 and PC2 accounted for the majority of the observed variations, providing insights into the shape distribution of *Eremias velox*.

Overall, the research underscores the importance of morphological studies in understanding species' ecological roles and evolutionary adaptations. The methodologies and findings contribute to the broader fields of taxonomy, conservation, and ecological management, with *Eremias velox* serving as a model organism for such studies.

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